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LANGUAGE TEACHING
IN DIGITAL CIVILIZATION:
CREATIVITY FOR TOTAL LEARNING

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LANGUAGE TEACHING IN DIGITAL CIVILIZATION: CREATIVITY FOR TOTAL LEARNING

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APPLYING THE TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL IN UNDERSTANDING ACADEMICS' BEHAVIOR TO ADOPT LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THEIR PROFESSION

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ABSTRACT

E-learning and blended learning is a familiar learning approach for students and lecturers alike in Indonesia and the ministry of high education even supports online learning as a way to increase people's accessibility to higher education programs. Pivotal to online learning is the presence of Learning Management System (LMS) that integrates learning, message, and evaluation tools in one place and connect lecturers to their students. Indonesian lecturers have harnessed LMS of various kinds to fulfill their teaching objectives and to assist students in their learning process. Finding the factors that make lecturers utilize LMS in their job is necessary to predict LMS' success in classroom. This paper presents a study using the technology acceptance model (TAM) as an attempt to analyze Indonesian lecturers' behavioral intention to use LMS, using the core constructs in TAM; perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and attitude toward usage. The study added lecturers' field of study and their amount of teaching hours as external variables. The result of this research suggests TAM was applicable in measuring Indonesian lecturers' behavioral intention to use LMS. Furthermore, it also confirms the original TAM's findings.

Keywords: *Learning management system, Technology Acceptance Model, online learning, higher education, Indonesia*

INTRODUCTION

Blended learning has been a ubiquitous learning approach in higher education for almost two decades (Güzer & Hamit, 2014; Becker, Cummins, Davis, Freeman, Hall, Giesinger, & Ananthanarayanan, 2017) and that is due to the rapid development of internet technology and learning management system. By fusing traditional face-to-face (FTF) class with online activities that are arranged pedagogically or substitute FTF time with online activities (Picciano, 2007), blended learning aims to enhance learners' knowledge and performance, accommodate personalized learning, provide higher learning experience, facilitate collaborative learning, and build learners' autonomy (Watson, 2008; Bonk, Kim, & Zeng, 2006; Marsh, 2012). Furthermore, Garrison & Kanuka reported that blended learning increased course completion rates, improved

retention, and increased students' satisfaction. As a result, blended learning opens the possibilities for synchronous and asynchronous learning activities in a thoughtful design (Garrison & Kanuka; 2004). To ensure the effective integration of FTF and online activities, teachers and students need a Learning Management System (LMS).

LMS is a software, web or desktop, that is used to deliver course content, record students' enrollment, track students' progress, assess students' comprehension, and facilitate teacher-student online interaction (Berking & Galagher, 2016; Dan Piedra, 2019). To achieve those aims, an LMS integrates a set of tools that belongs to three types: study tools, communication tools, and productivity tools (Wichadee, 2015). The study tools are discussion board, quiz, grade book, and feedback. Students can submit their assignments conveniently from time to time. For communication between teacher and students, an LMS has messaging and announcement features. This way, students are able to consult their teachers with ease. For productivity, teachers and students can use calendar, cloud storage service (Google Drive or Dropbox), Office online, and assignment submission. All these tools turn an LMS into a centralized source of learning where teachers can create course class and modules that contain learning materials (PDF, Office docs, video, pictures), assignments, and quizzes; students can access the modules anytime anywhere and they can do their assignments individually or in a group. In addition, teachers can monitor students learning progress and performance in the LMS. From that data, teachers provide feedbacks to improve students performance (Goh, Hong, & Gunawan, 2014; Kadir & Aziz, 2016; Watson, 2017; Holmes & Pietro-Rodriguez, 2018).

With the rise of online learning and blended learning, LMS is an indispensable tool in blended learning or online learning program. LMS' users are mostly K-12, higher education institutions (HEI), and training company (Bersin, 2017; Bowyer & Chambers, 2017, Davis, Carmean, & Wagner, 2009; Hill, 2017, Lim & Wang, 2017; Mtebe, 2015). To cater its wide range of users, LMSs come in three categories; proprietary LMS (commercial), open-source LMS, and cloud-base LMS (Dobre, 2015). Proprietary LMSs are license products that its vendors sell to any institution who is interested to use it and the LMSs are modifiable to suit clients' requests. The examples of proprietary LMSs are Blackboard, D2L, and eCollege. Open-source LMSs are publicly available and free of charge to all users who also have access to the source code. Moodle, and Sakai are two examples of open source LMSs. Google Classroom, Microsoft Classroom, and Apple Classroom are cloud-based LMS because they sit in the cloud and utilize a range of cloud-based tools that are developed by each vendor (University at Buffalo, n.d.) According to Edutechnica survey (2017), many HEIs and schools in US (500-2000 students) have adopted LMS as their online learning platform or blended learning purpose and 90% of the LMSs are of commercial type. Commercial LMS is favored because they are reliable, flexible, cost efficient, up-to-date, and convenient to use.

Outside US, the survey recorded an increase usage of proprietary LMS among schools and HEIs in Canada, UK, and Australia.

Generally, HEIs implement two kinds of LMS—“home grown” and proprietary (Wichadee, 2015). “Home grown” LMS is a system created and developed by a HEI and it is used exclusively by faculties and students of that particular HEI. This LMS exist when there was a few number of commercial LMS that meets HEI needs. However, many HEIs has shifted to proprietary, open-source, or cloud-based LMS because the cost of building, maintaining, and developing an exclusive LMS is higher than the cost of ready-to-use and customizable LMS from 3rd party vendors. Commercial LMS excels in its continuous update with the latest technology changes and trends (Davis, Carmean & Wagner, 2009; Ramani, 2017). Using proprietary LMS means that a HEI does not need to provide big budget for the maintenance and development of an LMS because it is the responsibility of the vendor.

Various researches have been done to study learners’ perceptions towards LMS and the result showed positive attitude toward LMS in supporting blended or online learning. Srichanyachon (2014) studied a group of EFL learners who studied Fundamental English course using blended learning approach and found that the students had positive perceptions about the use of LMS in blended learning situation. Another study by Chips, Kerr, Brysiewicz, and Walters (2015) also claimed that LMS assisted students in their learning process through its feedback and discussion features. The students stated that those two features helped them in consulting learning problems and doing reflection. In 2017, Holmes and Pietro-Rodriguez conducted studied of students’ perceptions of LMS in a teacher education program and they found that the students enjoyed the flexibility of accessing course materials and appreciated highly the online quiz feature in LMS due to its instantaneous feedback. A research on teachers of a secondary school in Padang further supports the notion that Edmodo (an LMS in the form of social media platform) motivates teachers in the implementation of blended learning because it was user-friendly (Yanti, Setiawan, Nurhabibah & Yanuar, 2017).

On the other side, an LMS can pose problems to both students and faculties as well. A research on the use of an LMS among students and lecturers in an IT school (Goh et al, 2014) gave a contrasting display among the faculties. Though students thought that Moodle is easy to use, the lecturers were confused and unsatisfied with the organization of content in Moodle. In addition, both students and lecturers treated the LMS merely as content repository and they did not try use the interaction tool, such as discussion forum. Online discussions among students or between students and teachers happened mostly in Facebook because it is available in mobile platform and eases teachers in tracking discussion from time to time using their mobile devices. In Borboa, Joseph, Spake, and Yazdanparast study (2014), students thought that chatline and class roster features in LMS did not enhance learning. So, the LMS’ features that most of them considered important in improving learning were syllabus, assignments, course materials, online

tests/quizzes, announcement, and calendar. In Chips et al (2015) study, age could influence students' attitude toward the use of LMS. Students who came from paper-based system, old generation, had trouble adapting to learning by using LMS because they did not have enough training on using internet and LMS. In terms of teaching staff, the study recognized the importance of training teachers or instructors on how to use LMS appropriately and optimally. In a study of LMS use in teacher preparation program, Holmes et al (2017) found that the students' classroom attendance decreased when learning materials were available online and the teaching staff perceived that condition with negative favor. Then, the study also found that the online quiz tool in LMS received the highest rating from students but the same condition did not happen with LMS' discussion board. Apparently, student-student discussions took place mostly in social media platforms than in LMS and they were not interested to use discussion tool in LMS unless teachers use it as assessment.

THEORITICAL FRAMEWORK

The aims of this study are to find out the attitudes and perceptions of Indonesian lecturers on using LMS to support the teaching learning process in their classrooms. To achieve the objective, the study used the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) which could explain the factors of computer acceptance and gives general description of users behaviors regardless of the level of users' computer skill (Davis, Bagozzi, & Warshaw, 1989). TAM proposes that user acceptance of computer technology is influenced by perceived usefulness (PU), perceived ease of use (PEOU), and attitude toward usage (A). PEOU is the degree of effort that users have to put in using a new technology. PU is defined as users' assumption on the possibility of a new technology to boost their performance. If the PEOU and PU are equal, users will form A (positive or negative) that will drive the behavioral intention to use the new technology. Therefore, the decision to use a computer system depends on whether it will improve users' performance.

This research chose TAM as its framework because it has strong empirical validation and provided high quality results (Alshammari, Ali & Rosli, 2016). Many studies have shown that PU, PEOU, and A have strong influence that affects users to accept technology. Perceived ease of use of a commercial LMS made students in a Jordanian university accepted the LMS in their study whereas the university adopted the LMS based on perceived usefulness (Majdalawi, Almarabeh, Mohammad, 2014). On another study in 2014, Alharbi and Drew found that as users PEOU increased, the PU increased accordingly. On the other side, the study also found that the lack of LMS availability did not make academics think that LMS is difficult to use. Another TAM-based research on a group of students in Malaysia (Juhary, 2014) discovered that the students had positive attitude toward LMS because they felt its contents helped them in their learning process. One more study using TAM framework proved that system quality had a positive effect on PEOU and PU of an LMS and it showed faculties' strong

external variables

Perceived Usefulness

Attitude toward using (A)

Behavioral Intention to Use (BI)

preference on quality issues (functions, content, navigation speed, interaction capability) of an LMS (Fathema, Shannon, Ross, 2015).

Besides user's PEOU, PU, and A toward technology, gender and age determines users' acceptance of a particular technology because the two factors bring different experience in using a technology tool. In some studies, scholars reported that females showed negative attitudes and lack of confidence in using technology (Anderson & Haddad, 2005; Dhindsa & Shahrizal- Emran, 2011; Li & Kirkup, 2007). On the other hand, females demonstrated better use of computer-mediated platforms like Blackboard and have been outperforming males academically (DeNeui & Dodge, 2006) while another found no significant difference in engagement in a discussion forum between males and females (Machado, 2011). As time progresses, both female and male users exhibited positive attitude in adopting technology in online or blended learning (Wichadee, 2015; Gomez, 2015). In Wang, Wu, and Wang's study (2009), it was the users' level of expectancy, not the age nor gender, that influenced technology acceptance in mobile learning. Interestingly, the same study showed that older users thought that they had to put more effort in mobile learning than younger users. When it comes to results of online learning using LMS, gender showed no role because the students' effort was highly correlated to their higher final grades (Lowe, 2016). Since this study gathered data from lecturers coming from multiple disciplines, the issue of subject domains they possessed, and the amount of their teaching hours per semester were taken into consideration too.

As blended learning has become very popular in HEI in Indonesia, this study was designed to examine the factors that influenced lecturers attitude, PEOU, and PU toward LMS usage and the actual use of LMS in HEIs, private or government institutions. The emphasis of this study was the lecturers' willingness to use LMS and a model was developed to explain considerable factors:

Table 1. Flowchart of Technology Acceptance Model

Research Questions

This study aims to answer the four questions below:

1. What are the lecturers attitude, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness toward LMS?
2. Is there any relation between lecturers' attitude, PEOU, and PU toward LMS?
3. Are there any differences in the lecturers' attitude, PEUO, and PU toward LMS between those who teach humanity subjects and science subjects?
4. Does the amount of teaching hour affect lecturers' attitude, PEOU, and PU toward LMS?
5. What are the difficulties faced by lecturers in using LMS?
6. What are the reasons why lecturers did not use LMS in their course?

Methodology

Instrumentation

To collect data, this study uses an online questionnaire that was a modification of Wichadee's instrument (2015) for her research on the factors related to faculties' attitude in adopting an LMS. Prior to data collection, the researcher has obtained Mrs. Wichadee's permission to use her instrument and he was allowed to modify it to suite his research purpose. The questionnaire consisted of five sections. The first section collected personal data about respondent's age, gender, teaching field, educational level, amount of teaching duty in one semester, and years of teaching experience. Section two was composed of eight items that measured respondents' attitude toward LMS. Then, the third section was made up of eight items that assessed lecturers' perceived ease of use. The items in section two and three were constructed on a five-point like Likert scale from strongly agree (=5) to strongly disagree (=1). The fourth section was designed to investigate respondents' perceived usefulness of LMS by providing five items that could be answered with "yes" or "no" by respondents. The last sections contained two open-ended questions in which the first question inquired the difficulties of using LMS, for those who used it, and the second question examined the reasons of not using an LMS, for those who did not use it.

For ease of data collection, the questionnaire was written in Indonesian because the target respondents were Indonesian and some of them did not have English proficiency. The questionnaire items were constructed using the data analysis obtained in Wichadee's paper (2015), so the questionnaire for this study had similarities to Wichadee's data instrument. To save time and cost, the questionnaire was distributed online using Google Form because it was a popular survey platform for online survey in Indonesia. Another benefit of Google Form is its ability to instantly tabulates data in charts every time a respondent fills an online survey and the tabulated data is automatically stored in Google Drive that can be accessed anytime and anywhere with strong protection from data lost.

Respondents

The online survey was sent to 21 lecturers, who were the colleagues of the researcher, via email and shared in three online groups of lecturers; one in a Whatsapp group and two in Facebook Group. The nature of data collection was voluntary so this study could not determine how many exactly target respondents who did the survey. The researcher invited his colleagues to fill the questionnaire and, after a month, the survey was able to gather 66 respondents from humanity and science field subjects from both state and private universities. Respondents were not required to sign any consent form because it was anonymous, did not collect respondents' names nor their email addresses.

Data Analysis

Data were collected and statistically tabulated by Google Form's automatic feature. Personal information of the participants was calculated for frequency and percentage. The data for attitude, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness were analyzed to find median and percentage because it was the recommended way to process ordinal data collected with Lickert scale (Kostoulas, 2013; Sullivan & Artino, 2013; Decker, 2018). For open-ended questions, respondents' responses were categorized into four groups based on the similarity of their ideas.

FINDINGS

Respondents' information

The online survey gathered data from 66 respondents; 27 males and 39 females; who were lecturers teaching in HEIs around Indonesia. 48 of the respondents taught in the field of humanities and 18 taught in the field of science. In terms of academic qualification, 53 respondents have Master degree and 18 of them hold Doctoral degree. As to teaching experience in HEI, 17 respondents have long teaching experience (>15 years), 27 respondents have moderate teaching experience (5-15 years), and 22 respondents have short teaching experience (>2 years). With regard to amount of teaching duties in each semester, 19 respondents teach for more than 12 hours a week, 21 teach for 12 hours, 16 teach 8 hours, and 10 teach 6 hours. The age group of respondents were varied, in which, 42.4% belonged to 30-39 years old, 31.8% belonged to 40-49 years old, 16.7% belonged to 25-30 years old, and a mere 9.1% was >50 years old. All respondents know LMS and have used it in one form or another in their teaching fields.

Research Question 1: How are the lecturers attitude, perceived ease of use, and perceived usefulness toward LMS?

Respondents PEOU toward LMS

Table 2. Findings of lecturers' PEOU toward LMS.

PEOU toward LMS		Mode	Frequency	Percentage	Median
1.	Easy to upload files to LMS	5	28	42.4%	4
2.	Easy to post a message in LMS	4	32	48.5%	4
3.	Easy to communicate with students in LMS	4	29	43.9%	4
4.	Easy to create quizzes	4	26	39.4%	4
5.	Easy to modify learning materials stored in LMS	5	29	43.9%	4
6.	Easy to check students' attendance in LMS	4	28	42.4%	4
7.	Easy to share website links	5	35	53%	5
8.	Easy to contact students using emails	4	28	42.4%	4

In terms of ease of use, respondents' perceived LMS as an easy-to-use software and that was clearly showed in the significant increase of approval scores, above 40% for most items, with exception for item four. Item seven received the highest approval in which link sharing via LMS was considered very easy to do. The data of PEOU also gave an insight that respondents could utilize the common features found in LMS; study tools, communication tools, and assessment tools.

Respondents PU toward LMS

Table 3. Findings of lecturers' PU toward LMS.

PU toward LMS		Yes	Means	No	Means
1.	Easy to communicate with students in LMS	48	0.72	18	0.27
2.	Easy to prepare and distribute learning materials in LMS	62	0.93	4	0.06
3.	Mudah mahasiswa di dalam LMS	47	0.71	19	0.28
4.	Easy to monitor students involvement in LMS	53	0.80	13	0.19
5.	Easy to give assignment to students by LMS	61	0.92	5	0.07

With regards to PU, the majority of respondents thought LMS was very useful to accomplish all the duties that were described in section 3's items. Respondents expressed positive favor toward LMS' usefulness in terms of providing lesson materials, interacting with students, and giving-collecting assignments. These responses meant that respondents' PU of LMS was consistent with their PEOU.

Table 4. Findings of lecturers' attitude toward LMS.

Attitude toward LMS		Mode	Frequency	Percentage	Median
1.	LMS that I use has features to evaluate learning process	4	29	43,9%	4
2.	LMS assists me in organizing learning materials	4	29	43,9%	4
3.	LMS eases communication between me and my students	4	24	36.4%	4
4.	LMS that I use provide space for independent learning	5	30	45.5%	4
5.	LMS that I use eases learning process	5	29	43,9%	4
6.	LMS that I use increase students and lecturers' interaction	5	22	33.3%	4
7.	LMS that I use increase students motivation in learning	4	28	42.2%	4
8.	LMS makes me change the way I teach	4	32	48.5%	4

As shown in Table 4, respondents showed positive attitude toward LMS in helping them to do their academic duties as proved in the percentage number and median. In data collection, item four, five, and six received highest rating. These numbers meant that many respondents' agreed with the questionnaire items.

Research Question 2: Are there any relationships between the lecturers' attitude toward LMS, perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, and their actual use of LMS

The analysis of data in Table 2, 3, and 4 proved that respondents PEOU and PU of LMS influenced their attitude positively and that made respondents willing to adopt LMS. Realizing that an LMS has tools that support lecturers' needs and purposes, respondents positively adopt LMS as technology that gives constructive and productive contribution to teaching and learning process inside and outside classroom.

Research Question 3: Are there any differences in the respondents' attitude, PEUO, and PU toward LMS between those who teach humanity and science subjects?

Based on the tabulated data of online survey, it was found that 72.7% of the respondents was from humanity studies and 27.3% was from science field. After analyzing the same data, which has been broken down in the category of field of study, the research found that the lecturers from science and humanities groups shared similar PEOU, PU, and attitude toward LMS. Although the data showed differences in four items in the survey, they were insignificant because the differences were of very small.

Research Question 4: Does the amount of teaching hour affect respondents' attitude, PEUO, and PU toward LMS?

In addition to field of study, this research investigated if the amount of teaching hour affects lecturer PEUO, PU, and attitude toward LMS that they are using. The online survey record showed that the respondents were divided into four groups. *Standar Nasional Pendidikan Tinggi* (National Standar of Higher Education) 2015 states that 1 sks equals to 45 minutes of teaching in the classroom. From that definition, the biggest group of respondent was the 12 sks (31.8%), teaching 540 hours/semester. The second group was the >12 sks (28.8), teaching more than 540 hours/semester. In third position, the 8 sks group (24.2%) and it was followed the 6 sks group (15.2%).

The survey revealed that the responses from four groups had similar result to research question 1. Despite differences in the numbers, all group of respondents showed positive attitude toward LMS usefulness and that attitude was influenced by their perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of the LMS. The differences in numbers are insubstantial as it cannot affect the whole data.

Research Question 5: What are the difficulties faced by lecturers in using LMS?

The responses from 66 respondents showed that their difficulties with LMS fall into three categories; internet connection, LMS' user experience, and students' lack of attention to LMS. When it comes to internet, 21 respondents were not satisfied with its speed and stability. Connection problem made both lecturers and their students had a problem of accessing LMS and its contents. The second problem was LMS' learning curve. Five respondents stated that it took a while for them to use LMS and to take advantage of its features. Another issue that came up was students' low diligence in checking the latest content update that lecturers had uploaded in the LMS. Four respondents stated that their students' had little care in checking the LMS for an update about the latest assignment or quizzes or learning materials.

Research Question 6: What are the respondents' reasons for not using LMS?

Based on respondents' responses, two stated that they did not use LMS because of lack of support from the institutions where they worked. One respondent wrote that his or her campus did not implement LMS because of budget efficiency. The other respondent commented that LMS adoption in his or her campus depended on rectorate's decision.

DISCUSSION

This study mainly aimed at validating the relationship between the PEOU and PU and how they were able to shaped respondents A in adopting LMS as part of their

teaching approach. Analysis of statistical data shows that when respondents perceived ease of use increased, the perceived usefulness increased correspondingly. Hence, their developed positive attitude toward LMS and its benefits. Interestingly, the difference of teaching hour and field of studies had no notable influence in respondents' decision to adopt LMS.

As to the respondents complaints about LMS, the explanation for their dissatisfaction can be described as follows. The lecturers disappointment of internet connection was probably caused by instability of internet service or infrastructures. To address the problem, campus should consult the internet provider to improve their service or improve the internet infrastructure in their campus. For learning curve, respondents' problem was probably due to little training or lack of assistance from IT department in their campus. HEIs that obligate their faculties to use LMS must create a manual for using the mandatory LMS and instruct the IT department to give constant assistance to faculties in using LMS. In response to students' lack of attention to LMS content, HEIs should use LMS that has mobile version app. If an LMS has a mobile version, students can access its contents anytime and anywhere without having to use computer and login into LMS' website. The advantages of LMS' mobile app are its ability to give quick notification whenever there is a new update and to let students accessing LMS from their smartphone or tablet.

CONCLUSION

On average, this study verified TAM's capacity to determine academics behavioral intention to use LMS. Specifically, it validates the relationship between perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, attitude toward usage, and its impact on intention to use a technology. Analysis of data collected by means of online survey confirms other findings based on TAM.

On the other hand, this study has limitations too. First, this study was limited by time. To accompany the data collected from online survey, an interview session was needed to give more data for cross reference, but doing interview was not possible because the respondents who filled the survey came from various places around Indonesia. So, it is going to be very difficult to visit each respondent and conduct interview with every one of them. Moreover, this study should not be generalized for three reasons. The respondents were from different HEIs; private and state institutions. Each institution may have different policy in the implementation of LMS, so the policy can influence lecturers' behavior and attitude in using LMS. In addition, the focus of this research was on the individual who used LMS and the number of respondents who did the survey was not equally distributed when they were grouped according to the amount of teaching hour and field of study. Future studies must obtain large size of respondents who are equally distributed in terms of teaching hour and fields of study. Finally, this

study analyzed the data using median and frequency to read respondents PEOU, PU, and A. It would be better if there is a reliability assessment using Cornbach Alpha.

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